

COUNCIL on LIBRARY and INFORMATION RESOURCES

Annual Report 2014–2015

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Contents

Acknowledgments	2
Directors, Staff, and Distinguished Presidential Fellows.....	4
Letter from the President	5
Programs and Activities.....	9
Fellows.....	20
Advisory Groups.....	22
Financial Statements	24

The Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR) is an independent, nonprofit organization that forges strategies to enhance research, teaching, and learning environments in collaboration with libraries, cultural institutions, and communities of higher learning. CLIR aspires to transform the information landscape to support the advancement of knowledge.

CLIR promotes forward-looking collaborative solutions that transcend disciplinary, institutional, professional, and geographic boundaries in support of the public good. In pursuing its mission, CLIR is committed to building trust, retaining independence, fostering collaboration, cultivating effective leadership, and capitalizing on strategic opportunities.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The following institutions and individuals provide crucial support for the activities and programs of the Council on Library and Information Resources (as of June 30, 2015).

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University of Alberta
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University of Arkansas
University of British Columbia
University of California, Berkeley
University of California, Irvine
University of California, Los Angeles
University of California, San Diego
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University of California, Santa Barbara
University of Chicago Library
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Research Library
Macalaster College
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
McGill University
McMaster University
Metropolitan New York Library Council
Middle Tennessee State University
Montana State University
National Archives and Records
Administration
National Library of Medicine
New York Public Library
New York University
North Carolina State University Libraries
Northeastern University
Northwestern University Library
OCLC Research
The Ohio State University
Oregon State University
Pennsylvania State University,
University Libraries
Princeton Theological Seminary
Princeton University Library
Purdue University
Reed College
Rhodes College
Rice University
Smithsonian Institution Libraries
Stanford University
Stony Brook University Libraries
Swarthmore College
Temple University
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University of California, Irvine
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University of California, Riverside
University of California, San Diego
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The Johns Hopkins University

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LESLIE WEIR
University of Ottawa

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Haverford College

GENE WIEMERS
Bates College

KARIN WITTENBORG**
University of Virginia

** Elected May 2015*

*** Term concluded November 2014*

**** Term concluded May 2015*

Staff as of June 30, 2015

LIZZI ALBERT
Administrative Coordinator

ALICE BISHOP
Senior Program Officer

NICOLE FERRAILOLO
Program Officer for Scholarly Resources

CHARLES HENRY
President

SHARON IVY WEISS
Chief Operating Officer

LOUISA KWASIGROCH
Director of Development and Outreach

ADAM LEADER-SMITH
Program Associate

AMY LUCKO
Director of Program Administration

BETHANY NOWVSKIE
Director, Digital Library Federation

KATHLIN SMITH
Director of Communications

CHRISTA WILLIFORD
Director of Research and Assessment

Distinguished Presidential Fellows

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Association of Research Libraries

JOHN UNSWORTH
Brandeis University

LETTER from the PRESIDENT

Charles Henry
President

Another productive, celebratory year for CLIR: the Council continues to flourish, expand its membership, and integrate with programs, projects, and issues of international reach.

Prominent new staff appointments this year include Bethany Nowvskie, who arrived in April as the director of the Digital Library Federation (DLF), and Nikki Ferraiolo, program officer for scholarly resources. Bethany brings a wealth of scholarship, teaching, and mentoring skills to DLF and CLIR. Her work at the Scholar's Lab at the University of Virginia, her leadership in the international flourishing of digital humanities over the past decade and the increasing awareness of this field of research as integral to the evolution of the grand tradition of humanistic inquiry, and her foundational role promoting the concept and beneficial consequences of alternative careers in the academy will strengthen the mission of DLF and attract an ever-widening constituency.

Nikki brings program and research expertise from her work at Columbia, both as a masters' student and as program manager in the history department. She joined CLIR just before the launch of the new digitizing hidden collections program and has brought great energy and intelligence to the effort in its first year. She was also a key organizing force behind the Hidden Collections Symposium—the capstone event for the seven-year cataloging program—in March 2015.

The appointment in June 2014 of Michael Edson, director of web and new media strategy at the Smithsonian Institution, as CLIR Distinguished Presidential Fellow also marks an important augmentation to CLIR's mission. Michael is widely recognized as an articulate futurist who explores the potential of technology for museums and archives as a means to better understand our growing dependence on visual culture. Michael's vision is ably expressed in a proposal he brought to CLIR this spring: Openlab, a project that will serve as instigator, incubator, and digital studio to accelerate the adoption of technologies and best practices across libraries, galleries, archives, and museums to catalyze sector-wide change.

This year also marked the publication of well-received research studies and reports. Two epitomize the range of CLIR's purview. The *ARSC Guide to Audio Preservation* was commissioned in response to the severe risk of media deterioration and the limited funding to address this crisis. The guide is a practical introduction to caring for and preserving audio collections. It is aimed at individuals and institutions that have recorded sound collections but lack the expertise in one or more areas to preserve them. *The Changing Landscape of Library and Information Services: What Presidents, Provosts, and Finance Officers Need to Know* is a report that elaborates upon a productive meeting of CLIR's CIOs in which key contemporary issues and challenges in library and technology services were enumerated.

CLIR received several important grants this year; of particular note was the generous support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation for the Digitization of Hidden Special Collections and Archives. This grant inaugurates the new iteration of the national competition begun with the Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives program. Our digitization program aspires to encourage approaches to digitization that make possible new kinds of scholarship in the digital research environment; support the digitization of entire collections; promote strategic partnerships; promote best practices for ensuring the long-term availability and discoverability of digital content; and ensure that digitized content is made available to the public as easily and completely as possible. In addition to producing a wealth of digital objects of great cultural value, a salient goal is to facilitate the adoption of standards and best practices that will result in a coherent, sustainable academic digital library of unprecedented scope.

New to this year's annual report is the category of Affiliates. We are using the term in a general way, to indicate a close programmatic alliance or association—a working relationship with many possible characteristics. The organizations listed bring to CLIR a variety of mutually beneficial opportunities. For example, NITLE is a program temporarily housed within CLIR as we work with its constituency to determine the services and resources that would help reinvigorate the institution; NITLE may remain a part of CLIR if its members so recommend. The International Interoperable Image Framework (IIIF) is an affiliate by virtue of our promotional support of the framework, our assistance with administering finances, and our mentoring of staff IIIF plans to hire in the coming years. These and other organizations that joined us subsequent to June 2015, including the National Digital Stewardship Alliance (NDSA) and the iSchool Consortium, offer a rich diversity of perspectives and interests while at the same time collectively strengthening our mission: collaborating with libraries, cultural institutions, and communities of higher learning to enhance research, teaching, and learning.

It is, as always, a privilege to work with the exceptionally talented staff at CLIR and our supportive Board of Directors. Many who are new to CLIR or know us by the volume of projects and research we produce believe the organization is three or four times its actual size; this is a tribute to the work capacity and dedication of our exemplary team.

Next year marks the 60th anniversary of CLIR: an opportunity to reflect upon decades of achievements and contributions to higher education and our role in promoting the public good of shared, open information. With the ongoing support of our sponsors and members, this landmark anniversary will be memorable as well as a pivot to further substantive work in realizing a vision as succinct as it is powerful: to transform the information landscape to support the advancement of knowledge.

Charles Henry

President

December 2015

416 people
attended the 2014
DLF Forum

\$4 million
granted in the
Hidden Collections
program

**CLIR'S
REACH**
this year

Over 200 CLIR
sponsors and DLF
members

36 attended the
2015 Leading
Change Institute in
Washington, DC

42 Postdoctoral
Fellows received
grants

15 Mellon
Dissertation
Fellowships
awarded

Four reports,
numerous blog posts,
and 6 newsletters
published

PROGRAMS and ACTIVITIES

July 1, 2014–June 30, 2015

DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Objective: Promote research, skill development, and collaboration to strengthen the digital infrastructure supporting all facets of the scholarly communication cycle.

Digital Library Federation Program

Strategy meets practice at the Digital Library Federation (DLF).

Through its programs, working groups, and initiatives, DLF connects CLIR's vision and research agenda to an active network of practitioners working in digital libraries, archives,

labs, and museums. DLF is a place where ideas can be road-tested, and from which new strategic directions can emerge.

The Digital Library Federation is a robust and diverse community of practitioners who advance research, learning, and the public good through the creative design and wise application of digital library technologies. DLF serves as a resource and catalyst for collaboration among archives, libraries and library service organizations, publishers, labs, museums, professional organizations, vendors, and all who are invested in digital library issues. The organization promotes work on standards and best practices; research and data management across disciplines; aggregation and preservation services for digital collections; digital library assessment; and services that expand access to resources for research, teaching, and learning.

In April 2015, Bethany Nowviskie became director of the DLF, succeeding Rachel Frick, who left the organization in September 2014. Widely known

as a pioneer and leading force in the digital humanities, Nowviskie had been a distinguished presidential fellow at CLIR, president of the Association for Computers and the Humanities, and director of the internationally-known Scholars' Lab at the University of Virginia Library. Among her goals for the coming year at DLF are increasing support for DLF's working groups, improving communications and the organization's web presence, deepening programmatic ties between DLF and CLIR, strengthening DLF's connections with the national and international digital stewardship community, continuing to build a vibrant liberal arts colleges cohort within the DLF, and exploring intersections between digital library and museums practice.

DLF Forum. The DLF Forum is convened annually and is open to digital library practitioners from member institutions and the broader community. The Forum serves as a meeting place, marketplace, and congress. As a meeting place it provides an opportunity for DLF working groups, affiliated organizations, and community members to conduct business and

present their work. As a marketplace of ideas, the Forum provides an opportunity to disseminate experiences and develop best practices, and to support a broader level of information sharing among digital library professionals. As a congress, the Forum provides an opportunity for the DLF to continually review and assess its programs with input from the community at large.

The 2014 DLF Forum, held October 27–29 in Atlanta, Georgia, drew a record 416 participants. Many of the sessions, including keynote addresses presented by Bethany Nowviskie and Bonnie Tijerina, were livestreamed and are available through the DLF website. In addition, a series of blog posts, contributed by recipients of DLF New Professionals Fellowships, DLF Forum Fellowships for

Underrepresented Groups, and DLF Cross-Pollinator Awards, provide personal perspectives on the Forum. Affiliated events included the Ada Initiative's Allies Workshop and the Taiga Forum.

Present at the 2014 Forum were representatives of several liberal arts colleges, and liberal arts college representation in the DLF community continues to grow. To better serve this community, in February 2015 DLF announced that it would host a Liberal Arts Colleges Preconference, preceding the 2015 Forum in Vancouver.

The 2014 Forum also welcomed four highly accomplished museum practitioners, thanks to generous support from the Samuel H. Kress Foundation for a new program for Museum Cross-Pollinator Fellows. Fellows each

shared reflections in a series of blog posts after the Forum, often highlighting the goals and challenges libraries and museums have in common.

Digital Library Assessment. A new and highly active DLF Digital Library Assessment group was formed in 2014. This group plans to meet in person during the DLF Forum to share problems, ideas, and solutions, and work year-round through a dedicated email list and a DLF-supported wiki. Membership is open to anyone interested in learning about or collaborating on the improvement of digital library assessment measures. Current subcommittees are focusing on tools and best-practices documents to support cost assessment, to measure digital library analytics, to standardize digital library content citations, and to assess user needs and usability. White papers and other work products will be made available throughout the year.

DLF eResearch Network

The DLF eResearch Network (eRN), created in 2014, is a cohort-based learning and networking experience meant to help academic and research libraries devise collaborative strategies for data management support. eResearch Network members develop plans appropriate for their institutions through collaboration, resource sharing, webinars, and custom consultations by eRN faculty. Network members come from colleges and universities of varying size. To date, 13 institutions from across the United States and Canada have participated in the eRN.

The 2014 eRN cohort concluded its work in November 2014. Over the course of the six month program, 24 participants from 8 institutions developed data management surveys, identified and filled needs for repository software, conducted outreach with local scholars and administrators, and piloted educational workshops. Participants consistently emphasize the value of peer-to-peer interaction in the eRN. “The DLF eRN faculty, fellows, and peers gave us valuable feedback on the current state of our research data services, and based on the eRN experience, we are moving forward with a data management needs assessment and a data repository pilot,” said Mayu Ishida, research services librarian at the University of Manitoba. Together with fellow 2014 eRN participant Kathleen Fear, data librarian at the University of Rochester, Ishida led a panel on “The Role of Assessment in Research Data Services” at the Research Data Access and Preservation (RDAP) summit in 2015.

The 2015 DLF eRN cohort kicked off with an in-person meeting in April,

Institutional Participants 2014 and 2015, DLF eResearch Network

California Institute of Technology
Colgate University
Montana State University
Northwestern University
Temple University
University of Arizona
University of Florida
University of Illinois at
Urbana-Champaign
University of Manitoba
University of Nevada Las Vegas
University of Richmond
University of Rochester
University of Toronto

co-located with the RDAP summit in Minneapolis. Work is expected to conclude with a meeting at the 2015 DLF Forum in Vancouver.

Digitizing Special Formats Wiki. The Digital Library Federation is now curating a list of resources for professionals planning projects involving the digitization of rare and unique materials. The list may be of special interest to CLIR Hidden Collections applicants and grantees, and includes introductory and reference materials that are good places to begin exploring issues relevant to digitizing cultural heritage.

Study on Needs in Continuing Education for Managing Cultural Heritage Data

In September 2013, the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS) awarded CLIR a grant to examine federally mandated plans for open access and their implications for continuing education needs for libraries, museums, and other cultural heritage institutions. Under this grant, CLIR is conducting research in three areas. Part 1 is a highly structured content analysis of select federal agency plans for supporting open access to data and publications, identifying the commonalities and differences among the plans with emphasis on access to data. Part 2 takes the results of the content analysis and traces its implications for IMLS program areas and the cultural heritage institutions they serve. Part 3 identifies gaps in continuing education opportunities for cultural heritage professionals, assessing the readiness of the current professional workforce and identifying how best to address the needs and close the gaps in the immediate and longer term. Final results will be released in spring 2016.

Committee on Coherence at Scale

CLIR established the Committee on Coherence at Scale for Higher Education in October 2012, in partnership with Vanderbilt University. The committee's charge is to examine emerging national-scale digital projects and their potential to help transform higher education in terms of scholarly productivity, teaching, cost-efficiency, and sustainability. The Committee currently comprises 24 members, representing university and college presidents and provosts, heads of national education associations and other organizations, and library and i-school deans. The Committee meets twice yearly.

In spring 2015, the University of Pittsburgh's iSchool announced the first two iFellows under the new doctoral fellowship program for information science students that support research for the Committee on Coherence at Scale. Timothy Schultz, PhD student at Drexel University's iSchool, and Wei Jeng, PhD student at the University of Pittsburgh's iSchool, were selected from a competitive pool of applicants. Timothy Schultz's research will dive into the world of "big data" as it pertains to collaborating, visualizing, and sharing information in the medical industry. Wei Jeng's research

will focus on her interest in information sharing, with an emphasis on investigating how scholars communicate and share research data with one another. The program, funded by an award from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, will ultimately support 10 iFellows in total.

SCHOLARSHIP and RESEARCH

Objective: Explore and assess new research methodologies, emerging fields of inquiry, intellectual strategies involving data gathering and collaboration, and modes of communication, including sharing of research data and publishing models, that are likely to define the next generation of scholars.

Postdoctoral Fellowship Program

CLIR's Postdoctoral Fellowship Program offers recent PhD graduates an opportunity to work on projects that forge and strengthen connections among library collections, educational technologies, and current research. Launched in 2004, the program has supported 130 fellows at 60 host institutions across the United States and Canada.

Since 2012, in response to a growing recognition within the professional community that research data management posed particular challenges

to libraries and other departments serving today's researchers, CLIR expanded the program's focus to data curation. With grant support from the Alfred P. Sloan and Andrew W. Mellon Foundations, CLIR seeks to help host institutions establish staffing models, policies, resources, and services related to research data curation through matching those institutions with PhDs with expertise relevant to their needs.

In May 2015, CLIR announced the award of 14 postdoctoral fellowships: five Postdoctoral Fellowships in Academic Libraries, five CLIR/DLF Postdoctoral Fellowships in Data Curation for Visual Studies, and four CLIR/DLF Postdoctoral Fellowships in Data Curation for the Sciences and Social Sciences.

The Fellowships in Data Curation for Visual Studies were launched this year with funding from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. As a field, Visual Studies calls attention to the material, cultural, and historical contexts of all images, the relationship of the visual object to the viewer, and the act of seeing from a historical and cultural perspective. Scholars in this field analyze and interpret static images, as well as film and video resources, including oral histories, performance, art, and mass media. Through this program, CLIR/DLF seeks to raise awareness and build capacity for sound data management practice throughout the academy.

Click to see a snapshot of CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowships in Data Curation

In June 2015, CLIR received a grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation to fund a second cohort of data curation fellowships in Medieval Studies.

All new fellows attended a summer seminar, hosted at Bryn Mawr College, addressing issues faced by twenty-first-century libraries, including data curation and management, and provided an opportunity for fellows to participate in cohort-building activities. Fellows' supervisors joined the seminar for one day to discuss expectations and establish effective communication strategies.

Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives

Launched in 2008 with the support of The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR's Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Program announced its final round of 19 grants in December 2014. The program, which had supported efforts to expose unknown or underused cultural materials, has been succeeded by a new program to digitize hidden collections, described in the following section.

A capstone event for the Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives program was held in March 2015 at the Kislak Center for Special Collections, Rare Books and Manuscripts at the University of Pennsylvania Libraries. The symposium, titled "Innovation, Collaboration, and Models" was preceded by an unconference. The two-day event drew 172 participants, including representatives from 62 Hidden Collections projects. More than 75 presenters and discussion leaders contributed

2014 Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Awards

Adirondack Historical Association

Living with Wilderness: Enhancing Access to The Adirondack Museum Historic Photograph Collection, \$157,685

Appalshop, Inc.

We Still Scream: The Mountain Eagle/Tom and Pat Gish Archives, \$90,605

Bowling Green State University

Getting to the Core: Cataloging 45-RPM Records, \$64,064

Computer History Museum

Computer History Museum Archives Processing Project (CHM APP), \$274,560

Go For Broke National Education Center

Segregated Japanese American Military Units of World War II: A Collaborative Online Repository of Oral Histories, Photos and Documents, \$260,975

Haverford College

Quaker Diaries, Journals, Commonplace Books and Small Manuscript Collections, \$59,328

Johns Hopkins University

Processing the Globe Collection and Press, \$180,156

President and Fellows of Harvard College on behalf of the Harvard Medical School

Bridging the Research Data Divide:

Rethinking Long-term Value and Access for Historical and Contemporary Maternal, Infant and Child Research, \$367,602

Solomon R. Guggenheim Foundation

Illuminating New York's Art and Performance Heritage from the 1960s to the Present: Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum Archives Audiovisual Collections, \$122,208

Storefront for Art and Architecture

Arranging and Describing Storefront's Archive, \$115,600

The Board of Trustees of the University of Illinois

Cataloging Cavagna: Italian imprints from the Sixteenth through the Nineteenth Century, \$498,942

The Mariners' Museum Library

The Maritime World in Photographs: Cataloguing the Photo Negatives of The Mariners' Museum, \$325,500

The Rector and Visitors of the University of Virginia

Hidden in Plain Sight, \$221,379

The Regents of the University of California

La Raza Newspaper & Magazine Records: Providing Access to the Mexican American Civil Rights Movement, \$148,021

Trace Foundation/Latse Library

Tibetan Audio-Visual Collections at Trace Foundation's Latse Library, \$160,389

University of Kentucky Research Foundation

Action in Appalachia: Revealing Public Health, Housing, and Community Development Records in the UK Libraries Special Collections Research Center, \$156,439

Wellesley College

The Wellesley Centers for Women Records, 1974–, \$68,550

WGBH Educational Foundation

National Educational Television Collection Catalog, \$458,619

WHYY, Inc.

Fresh Air in the Sunlight: Opening Access to Forty Years of WHYY's Fresh Air with Terry Gross, \$254,769

More detail on this year's funded projects can be found at <http://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/awards/for-2014>.

to the program, vividly illustrating the impact the Hidden Collections initiative has had over its seven-year history. Grant recipients addressed problems that today's library and cultural heritage professionals face as they organize collections and make them accessible to scholars and other users. Symposium proceedings are available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub169>.

Since the program's inception, the program has awarded 129 grants amounting to \$27.5 million. Grants have gone to academic libraries, museums, public libraries, archives, and historical societies, among other types of cultural institutions. Through the grant program, one quarter of the funded projects were collaborative partnerships.

By June 2015, grant recipients reported the archival processing of at least 2,952 collections, extending a reported 53,608 linear feet, an additional

4,229 cubic feet, plus 960 boxes of mixed materials. Recipients have created item-level descriptions for a reported 273,728 items, including:

- 50,551 books and manuscripts;
- 46,702 audio and audiovisual recordings;
- 29,393 items of ephemera;
- 27,125 pamphlets;
- 15,600 pamphlet plays;
- 8,560 maps and map series;
- 6,956 artifacts;
- 5,537 artworks;
- 2,978 architectural drawings; and more.

Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives

In January 2015, CLIR announced a major new program to fund the digitization of rare and unique content in cultural memory institutions, thanks to a grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. The national competition is built upon the model of CLIR's Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives program. Developed through consultation with digital library practitioners and funders, and with input from the broader community, the program is designed to:

- encourage approaches to digitization that make possible new kinds of scholarship in the digital research environment
- support the digitization of entire collections, rather than selected items
- promote strategic partnerships, since few institutions have the capacity to handle and scan the wide array of objects in their collections
- promote best practices for ensuring the long-term availability and discoverability of digital files, and
- ensure that digitized content is made available to the public as easily and completely as possible.

Applicants submitted initial proposals by April 30, 2015; final proposals from those recommended for advancement by the program's review panel were due July 27, 2015. Decisions will be announced by January 2016, and CLIR expects to award about \$4 million.

Click on image to hear Mellon Dissertation Fellows talk about the impact of the fellowship on their work.

Ryan Kashanipour
CLIR Fellow, 2007
University of Arizona

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships

In 2015, 15 graduate students were selected to receive Mellon Dissertation Fellowships. The fellowship program, initiated in 2002, is intended to help graduate students in the humanities and related social science fields pursue doctoral research using original sources and gain skill and creativity in using original source materials in libraries, archives, museums, and related repositories. To date, the program has supported 194 graduate students who have carried out their dissertation research in public and private libraries and archives worldwide.

Plans are under way for an assessment of the program's reach and impact. A draft assessment, prepared by Lori Jahnke, anthropology librarian at Emory University, and Amanda Watson, comparative literature librarian at New York University, is scheduled for review late in 2015, and a formal report is anticipated in March 2016.

LEADERSHIP EDUCATION and CULTIVATION

Objective: Investigate and seek to define the skills and expertise needed to administer, inspire, and inform the next generation.

Leading Change Institute

CLIR and EDUCAUSE hosted the second Leading Change Institute (LCI) May 31–June 5, 2015. Thirty-six participants joined deans Elliott Shore, executive director, Association of Research Libraries; and Joanne Kossuth, vice president for operations and CIO, Olin College of Engineering. Following the LCI, participants were invited to join deans Shore and Kossuth for regular hour-long discussions, allowing them to continue exchanges beyond the Institute and to provide ongoing support and advice for one another.

LCI aims to prepare and develop the next generation of leaders in libraries, information services, and higher education by engaging those who seek to further develop their skills for the benefit of higher education.

Chief Information Officers Group

CLIR's Chief Information Officers Group is composed of 30 directors of organizations that have merged their library and technology units on liberal arts college and university campuses.

The group, which meets semi-annually, discussed the future of library and information technology services (LITS), and how their organizations should position themselves for that future at its December 2013 meeting. The discussion formed the basis for a white paper, written by CIOs Richard Holmgren of Allegheny College and Gene Spencer of Ursinus College,

Leading Change Institute Participants 2015

Jean-Pierre Bayard, California State University
Felicia Bianchi, Emory University
Morag Boyd, Ohio State University
Benjamin Canlas, University of Missouri
Niraj Chaudhary, University of Colorado Denver
Brad Christ, Southern Oregon University
Sean Connin, Trinity University
Bryce Cundick, University of Maine at Farmington
Jill Deupi, Lowe Art Museum
Beena Doolabh, AUT University
Greg Dumont, McDaniel College
Adam Edelman, Montana State University
David Esping, Missouri University of Science and
Technology
Tania Fersenheim, Brandeis University
Hannah Inzko, University of Miami
Kris Johnson, Montana State University, Bozeman
Karen Juday, University of Southern California
Steven Knowlton, University of Memphis
Pamela Louderback, Northeastern State University
Judith Molnar, Xavier University
Mark Newton, Columbia University
Todd Nicolet, University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Pratike Patel, Harvard Law School
Rebecca Pernell, Stanford University
Dale Pike, Virginia Polytechnic and State University
Ernest Pringle, University of South Carolina Aiken
Tamsyn Rose-Steel, Johns Hopkins University
Rob Rucker, North Carolina State University
Jessika Thomas, West Virginia University
Scott Tiner, Bates College
Jennifer Vandever, Southern Illinois University
Edwardsville
Anu Vedantham, University of Pennsylvania
Matthew Vest, University of Virginia
Bridget Wikidal, California State University
Mark Yeger, Bucknell University
Patrick Yott, Northeastern University

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group Members

(as of 6/30/15)

Suzanne Aber, Trinity College
Param Bedi, Bucknell University
Jim Cubit, Lake Forest College
Greg Diment, Kalamazoo College
Megan Fitch, Beloit College
Ronald Griggs, Kenyon College
Lee Hisle, Connecticut College
Rick Holmgren, Allegheny College
Robert Johnson, Rhodes College
Todd Kelley, Carthage College
Kenneth Kochien, Colby-Sawyer College
Roberta Lembke, St. Olaf College
Paul Mattson, Luther College
Pam McQuesten, Southwestern University
Kathy Monday, University of Richmond
Rick Provine, DePauw University

Ravi Ravishanker, Wellesley College
Robert Renaud, Dickinson College
Joanne Schneider, Iona College
Vicki Sells, Sewanee: The University of the South
Gina Siesing, Bryn Mawr College
Justin Sipher, St. Lawrence University
David Smallen, Hamilton College
Carol Smith, DePauw University
Gene Spencer, Ursinus College
Bruce Taggart, Lehigh University
John Unsworth, Brandeis University
Gene Wiemers, Bates College
Alex Wirth-Cauchon, Mount Holyoke College
Frank Wojcik, The College at Brockport, State University of New York

that CLIR issued in September 2014. *The Changing Landscape of Library and Information Services: What Presidents, Provosts, and Finance Officers Need to Know* explores emerging opportunities for colleges and universities, the potential role of LITS organizations in realizing that potential, and the core competencies that LITS organizations will need to support positive institutional change in the decade ahead.

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Kelly Grogg, a library and information sciences student at the University of Iowa, was selected to receive the 2015 Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship.

Grogg spent two years teaching at a rural high school in Cambodia through the United States Peace Corps. On her own initiative, she arranged for a large donation of books to the school's library with the promise of a trained librarian and open access for the students. "I was able to witness how a rural village was transformed by the access to information they were granted through this small library. It was this experience that ignited an inescapable desire to pursue a career in developing information access throughout the world."

Grogg has a B.A. in English Literature from the University of Iowa and works as a graduate research assistant in Special Collections and University Archives.

The Rovelstad Scholarship provides travel funds for a student of library and information science to attend the annual meeting of the World Library and Information Congress, which took place in Cape Town, South Africa, in August 2015.

AFFILIATES

National Institute for Technology in Liberal Education (NITLE)

In April 2015, it was announced that the National Institute for Technology in Liberal Education (NITLE) would migrate to CLIR from its home at Southwestern University on July 1, 2015, and that CLIR would oversee a rigorous analysis and assessment of the organization. The assessment, based on surveys and interviews, will identify the opportunities and challenges facing NITLE and is expected to be completed in February 2016.

PUBLICATIONS

- *The Changing Landscape of Library and Information Services: What Presidents, Provosts, and Finance Officers Need to Know*, by Richard Holmgren and Gene Spencer. September 2014.
- *The Center of Excellence Model for Information Services*, by Joy Kirchner, José Diaz, Geneva Henry, Susan Fliss, John Culshaw, Heather Gendron, and Jon E. Cawthorne. February 2015.
- *ARSC Guide to Audio Preservation*, Sam Brylawski, Maya Lerman, Robin Pike, Kathlin Smith, eds. May 2015.
- *Getting Found: SEO Cookbook*, by Patrick O'Brien and Kenning Arlitsch. May 2015.
- *CLIR Annual Report, 2013-2014*. December 2014.
- *CLIR Issues* 100–105.

FELLOWS

2015–2016 Postdoctoral Fellows

New Fellows

Reid Boehm

PhD Information Science, University of Tennessee, Knoxville
Host: University of Notre Dame

Jacquelyn Clements

PhD History of Art, Johns Hopkins University
Host: University of Toronto

Melissa Dinsman

PhD Literature, University of Notre Dame
Host: University of Notre Dame

Carrie Johnston

PhD English and American Literature, Southern Methodist University
Host: Bucknell University

Dimitrios Latsis

PhD Film Studies, University of Iowa
Host: Internet Archive

Chreston Miller

PhD Computer Science and Applications, Virginia Tech
Host: Virginia Tech

Kyle Parry

PhD Film and Visual Studies, Harvard University
Host: University of Rochester

Fernando Rios

PhD Geography, University of Buffalo, SUNY
Host: Johns Hopkins University

Elizabeth Rodrigues

PhD English, University of Michigan
Host: Temple University

Edward Triplett

PhD History of Art and Architecture, University of Virginia
Host: Duke University

Martin Tsang

PhD Anthropology, Florida International University
Host: University of Miami

Mary Lindsay Van Tine

PhD English and Comparative Literature, Columbia University
Host: Swarthmore College/University of Pennsylvania

Leila Walker

PhD English, City University of New York
Host: St. Lawrence University

Qian Zhang

PhD Physical Oceanography, Louisiana State University
Host: University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Continuing Fellows as of June 30, 2015

Laura Aydelotte

PhD English, University of Chicago
Host: University of Pennsylvania

Michael Bales

PhD Biomedical Informatics, Columbia University
Host: Weill Cornell Medical College

Sayan Bhattacharyya

PhD Comparative Literature, University of Michigan
Host: University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign/HathiTrust Research Center

Meaghan Brown

PhD English Literature, Florida State University
Host: Folger Shakespeare Library

Scout Calvert

PhD History of Consciousness, University of California, Santa Cruz
Host: University of California, Los Angeles

Morgan Daniels

PhD Philosophy in Information, University of Michigan
Host: Vanderbilt University

Rachel Deblinger

PhD History, University of California, Los Angeles
Host: University of California, Santa Cruz

Anne Donlon

PhD English, The City University of New York
Host: Emory University

Annie Johnson

PhD History, University of Southern California
Host: Lehigh University

Emily McGinn

PhD Comparative Literature, University of Oregon
Host: Lafayette College

Monica Mercado

PhD History, University of Chicago
Host: Bryn Mawr College

Paige Morgan

PhD English and Textual Studies, University of Washington
Host: McMaster University

Alice Motes

PhD Sociology, University of California, Irvine
Host: University of Minnesota

Tim Norris

PhD Environmental Studies, University of California at Santa Cruz
Host: University of Miami

Charlotte Nunes

PhD English, University of Texas at Austin
Host: Southwestern University

Jessica Otis

PhD History, University of Virginia
Host: Carnegie Mellon University

Philip Palmer

PhD English, University of Massachusetts Amherst
Host: University of California, Los Angeles

Alicia Peaker

PhD English Literature with Certificate in Women's Studies, Northeastern University
Host: Middlebury College

Sarah Pickle

PhD Comparative Literature, Cornell University
Host: Pennsylvania State University

Andrew Rechnitz

PhD English, The University of Texas at Austin
Host: Southwestern University

Meridith Beck Sayre

PhD History of Science, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Host: Indiana University

The Postdoctoral Fellows summer seminar at Bryn Mawr

Continuing Fellows, cont'd.

Emily Sherwood

PhD English, The City University of New York
 Host: Bucknell University

Plato Smith

PhD Library and Information Studies, Florida State University
 Host: University of New Mexico

Todd Suomela

PhD Communication and Information, University of Tennessee
 Host: University of Alberta

Yun Tai

PhD Sociology, Emory University
 Host: University of Virginia

Ana Van Gulick

PhD Psychology, Vanderbilt University
 Host: Carnegie Mellon University

2015–2016 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Jessica Arnett

University of Minnesota
Between Empires and Frontiers: Alaska Native Sovereignty and U.S. Settler Imperialism

Tania Bhattacharyya

Columbia University
Bombay, 1839–1932: Empire, Space, and Orders of Belonging in an Indian Ocean Port City

Antawan Byrd

Northwestern University
Interferences: Sound, Technology, and the Politics of Listening in Afro-Atlantic Art

Andrew Campana*

Harvard University
Poetry Across Media in 20th-Century Japan

Lucia Carminati

University of Arizona
Across the Mediterranean, 1863–1919: Italian Working-Class Migrants in Egypt and Practices of Cosmopolitanism

Emilie Connolly

New York University
Indian Trust Funds and the Routes of American Capitalism, 1795–1865

Mackenzie Cooley

Stanford University
Engineering the Animal: Breeding and the Quest to Perfect the Renaissance Body, 1450–1600

Lara Fabian

University of Pennsylvania
Between East, West, and the Steppe: The South Caucasus as the Northeastern Roman Borderland

Diana Garvin

Cornell University
All-Consuming: Food, Gender, and Power in Fascist Italy, 1922–1945

Elaine LaFay

University of Pennsylvania
Atmospheric Bodies: Medicine, Meteorology, and the Cultivation of Place in the Antebellum Gulf South

Jesse Lockard

The University of Chicago
A City Is Not a Picture: Yona Friedman, Megastructuralism and the Estrangement of Art and Architecture

Meekyung MacMurdie

University of Chicago
Geometric Medicine: Aniconism and Medieval Arab Painting

Ron Makleff

University of California, Berkeley
Monuments of Information: The Archives of State Formation in Northern Europe, c. 1380–1880

Chelsea Schields

The Graduate Center, City University of New York
Closer Ties: The Dutch Caribbean and the Aftermath of Empire, 1942–2012

Joohee Suh

Washington University in St. Louis
The Afterlife of Corpses: Dead Bodies, Ecology, and the Qing Culture of the Macabre in North China (1644–1911)

Andrew Welton

University of Florida
Forging Entanglements: The Spear in Early Medieval English Society

** subsequently withdrew acceptance*

ADVISORY GROUPS

as of June 30, 2015

Digital Library Federation Advisory Committee

Dan Cohen
Digital Public Library of America

Patricia Hswe
Pennsylvania State University

Max Marmor
Samuel H. Kress Foundation

Trevor Muñoz
University of Maryland Libraries

Stephen Rhind-Tutt
Alexander Street Press

David Rumsey
David Rumsey Map Collection and
Cartography Associates

Bess Sadler
Stanford University Library

Sarah Shreeves
IDEALS and Scholarly Commons

Winston Tabb
Johns Hopkins University

Jennifer Vinopal
New York University

2014 Hidden Collections Review Panel Final Proposal Phase

Michael Edson
Director, Web and New Media Strategy
Smithsonian Institution

Rachel Frick
Business Development Director
Digital Public Library of America

Charles Henry
President
CLIR

Mary Kelley
Professor
University of Michigan

Ronald L. Larsen
Dean and Professor
University of Pittsburgh

Jerome McGann
John Stewart Bryan University Professor
University of Virginia

Dennis Meissner
Head of Collections Management
Minnesota Historical Society

Stephen G. Nichols
James M. Beall Professor of French and
Humanities
Johns Hopkins University

Cheryl Oestreicher
Head of Special Collections and Archives/
Assistant Professor
Boise State University

Lynn Ransom
Project Manager, Lawrence J. Schoenberg
Database of Manuscripts
The University of Pennsylvania

Lisa Spiro
Director of NITLE Labs
National Institute for Technology in
Liberal Education (NITLE)

Richard V. Szary
Director, Louis Round Wilson Library
and Associate University Librarian for
Special Collections
University of North Carolina at Chapel
Hill

2015 Hidden Collections Review Panel Initial Proposal Phase

Jody DeRidder
Associate Professor and Head of Digital
Services
University of Alabama Libraries

Emily Gore
Director for Content
Digital Public Library of America

Charles Henry
President
CLIR

Geneva Henry
Vice Provost for Libraries and University
Librarian
The George Washington University

Lori Jahnke
Anthropology Librarian
Emory University

Ronald L. Larsen
Dean and Professor, School of
Information Sciences
University of Pittsburgh

**2015 Hidden Collections Review Panel
Initial Proposal Phase, *cont'd.***

Timothy Murray

Professor of Comparative Literature
and English and the Director of the
Society for the Humanities
Cornell University

Stephen G. Nichols

James M. Beall Professor of French and
Humanities
Johns Hopkins University

Lynn Ransom

Curator of Programs, Schoenberg
Institute for Manuscript Studies
University of Pennsylvania Libraries

Kathleen Smith

Germanic Studies Subject Specialist
Stanford University

Lisa Snyder

Visualization and Modeling Expert
Institute for Digital Research and
Education, University of California, Los
Angeles

Emily Thompson

Professor of History
Princeton University

Madelyn Wessel

University Counsel
Virginia Commonwealth University

Kimberly Christen Withey

Associate Professor of English, the
Associate Director of the Digital
Technology and Culture Program, and
the Director of Digital Projects at the
Plateau Center of Native American
Programs
Washington State University

**Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation
Research in Original Sources, Selection
Committee for 2015–2016 Fellows**

Jeffrey Ahlman

Smith College

Andrew Asher

Indiana University Bloomington

Alan Barenberg

Texas Tech University

Lydia Brandt

University of South Carolina

Mark Dimunation

Library of Congress

Pablo Palomino

University of California, Berkeley

Heather Waldroup

Appalachian State University

Bridget Whearty

Stanford University

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

**FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

**FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2015
WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT**

**STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia**

Council on Library and Information Resources

Table of Contents

	<u>Page</u>
Independent Auditors' Report	26–27
Statement of Financial Position.....	28
Statement of Activities and Changes in Net Assets.....	29
Statement of Cash Flows	30
Notes to Financial Statements	31–36
Schedule of Functional Expenses.....	37

STONE AND SPRING
CERTIFIED PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS
A Partnership of Professional Corporations

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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
Stephen C. Stone, C.P.A.

INDEPENDENT AUDITOR'S REPORT

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, DC

We have audited the accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources (a non-profit organization), which comprise the statement of financial position as of June 30, 2015, and the related statements of activities and change in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended, and the related notes to the financial statements.

Management's Responsibility for the Financial Statements

Management is responsible for the preparation and fair presentation of these financial statements in accordance with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America; this includes the design, implementation, and maintenance of internal control relevant to the preparation and fair presentation of financial statements that are free from material misstatement, whether due to fraud or error.

Auditor's Responsibility

Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit. We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free from material misstatement.

An audit involves performing procedures to obtain audit evidence about the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. The procedures selected depend on the auditor's judgment, including the assessment of the risks of material misstatement of the financial statements, whether due to fraud or error. In making those risk assessments, the auditor considers internal control relevant to the entity's preparation and fair presentation of the financial statements in order to design audit procedures that are appropriate in the circumstances, but not for the purpose of expressing an opinion on the effectiveness of the entity's internal control. Accordingly, we express no such opinion. An audit also includes evaluating the appropriateness of accounting policies used and the reasonableness of significant accounting estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall presentation of the financial statements.

We believe that the audit evidence we have obtained is sufficient and appropriate to provide a basis for our audit opinion.

Opinion

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2015, and the change in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in accordance with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Other Matter

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the financial statements as a whole. The schedule of functional expenses on page 37 is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the financial statements. Such information is the responsibility of management and was derived from and relates directly to the underlying accounting and other records used to prepare the financial statements. The information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the financial statements and certain additional procedures, including comparing and reconciling such information directly to the underlying accounting and other records used to prepare the financial statements or to the financial statements themselves, and other additional procedures in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. In our opinion, the information is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the financial statements as a whole.

Steve and Perry
Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
October 22, 2015

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2015

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporary Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Current Assets:			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 937,688	\$ 7,280,327	\$ 8,218,015
Investments	15,568	2,008,745	2,024,313
Accounts receivable	18,536	803,253	821,789
Total current assets	<u>\$ 971,792</u>	<u>\$ 10,092,325</u>	<u>\$ 11,064,117</u>
Furniture and equipment, net of accumulated depreciation	<u>\$ 55,659</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 55,659</u>
Other assets	103,684	-	103,684
Total Assets	<u>\$ 1,131,135</u>	<u>\$ 10,092,325</u>	<u>\$ 11,223,460</u>
Current Liabilities:			
Accounts payable	\$ 333,884	\$ -	\$ 333,884
Capital lease payable	3,333	-	3,333
Accrued expenses	118,724	-	118,724
Total Current Liabilities	<u>\$ 455,941</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 455,941</u>
Long Term Liabilities:			
Capital lease payable, net of current portion	<u>\$ 10,541</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 10,541</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 466,482</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 466,482</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 664,653</u>	<u>\$ 10,092,325</u>	<u>\$ 10,756,978</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u>\$ 1,131,135</u>	<u>\$ 10,092,325</u>	<u>\$ 11,223,460</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2015

	Unrestricted	Temporary Restricted	Total
Revenue			
Grants and contracts	\$ 7,242	\$ 7,674,460	\$ 7,681,702
Contributions	1,180,061	73,566	1,253,627
Leading change institute	198,000	-	198,000
Fellowship	102,500	-	102,500
Registration	181,776	-	181,776
Publication sales	1,628	-	1,628
Investment income	(1,982)	28,051	26,069
Other income	11,386	2,777	14,163
	<u>\$ 1,680,611</u>	<u>\$ 7,778,854</u>	<u>\$ 9,459,465</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions			
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 7,558,317</u>	<u>\$ (7,558,317)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 9,238,928</u>	<u>\$ 220,537</u>	<u>\$ 9,459,465</u>
Expenses			
Program services:			
Preservation and access	\$ 4,563,120	\$ -	\$ 4,563,120
Digital infrastructure	888,773	-	888,773
Leadership, education and cultivation	213,826	-	213,826
Other strategic initiatives	77,194	-	77,194
Communications and publications	272,921	-	272,921
Development	36,038	-	36,038
Outreach and collaboration	269,768	-	269,768
Scholarship and research	2,062,025	-	2,062,025
Total Program Services	<u>\$ 8,383,665</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 8,383,665</u>
Administration	<u>\$ 533,153</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 533,153</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 8,916,818</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 8,916,818</u>
Change in Net Assets	<u>\$ 322,110</u>	<u>\$ 220,537</u>	<u>\$ 542,647</u>
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>342,543</u>	<u>9,871,788</u>	<u>10,214,331</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 664,653</u>	<u>\$ 10,092,325</u>	<u>\$ 10,756,978</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the year ended June 30, 2015

Operating Activities	
Change in net assets	\$ 542,647
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) operating activities:	
Depreciation	16,431
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	14,487
(Increase) decrease in other assets	(27,966)
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	(788,678)
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	(62,065)
	<hr/>
Net Cash Provided (used) by Operating Activities	\$ (305,144)
Investing Activities	
Purchases of investments	\$ (2,528,000)
Sales of investments	2,773,248
Disposal of furniture and equipment	853
Purchases of furniture and equipment	(42,065)
	<hr/>
Net Cash Provided (Used) by Investing Activities	\$ 204,036
Financing Activities	
Principal payments on capital lease	\$ (3,092)
Net Cash Provided (Used) by Financing Activities	\$ (3,092)
	<hr/>
Net Change in Cash and Cash equivalents	\$ (104,200)
Cash and Cash Equivalents, Beginning of Year	<hr/> 8,322,215
Cash and Cash Equivalents, End of Year	<hr/> <hr/> \$ 8,218,015
Supplemental Cash Flow Information:	
Interest paid during the year	<hr/> <hr/> \$ 1,168

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2015

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council on Library and Information Resources is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council on Library and Information Resources operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council on Library and Information Resources conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council on Library and Information Resources reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council on Library and Information Resources are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs - Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2015
 (Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent grant receivable, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council on Library and Information Resources management has evaluated accounts receivable collection from prior years and has determined that an allowance for doubtful accounts is not necessary.

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council on Library and Information Resources records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments – Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2015 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

Subsequent Events- In preparing these financial statements, The Council on Library and Information Resources has evaluated events and transactions for potential recognition or disclosure through October 22, 2015, the date the financial statements were issued.

NOTE 3- Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

Furniture and equipment	\$ 126,283
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(70,623)</u>
	<u>\$ 55,659</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2015

(Continued)

NOTE 4- Investments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has adopted SFAS No. 124, "Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations." Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2015

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -
Bonds	-	-	-
Corporate fixed income	-	-	-
Government securities	-	-	-
Certificates of deposit	-	1,887	1,891,578
Mutual funds	<u>(1,157)</u>	<u>(16,374)</u>	<u>132,735</u>
Subtotal	<u>\$ (1,157)</u>	<u>\$ (14,487)</u>	<u>\$ 2,024,313</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>\$ 8,218,015</u>
Total	<u>\$ (1,157)</u>	<u>\$ (14,487)</u>	

The following schedule summarizes the investment and cash equivalent return and its classification in the statement of activities for the year ended June 30, 2015:

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	Temporarily <u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Interest and dividends	\$ 5,080	\$ 36,633	\$ 41,713
Realized gains (losses)	-	(1,157)	(1,157)
Unrealized gains (losses)	<u>(7,062)</u>	<u>(7,425)</u>	<u>(14,487)</u>
Total investment return	<u>\$ (1,982)</u>	<u>\$ 28,051</u>	<u>\$ 26,069</u>

NOTE 5 - Income Taxes

The Council on Library and Information Resources is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2015

(Continued)

NOTE 5 - Income Taxes (Continued)

The Organization is subject to income taxes in U.S. federal jurisdictions and various state jurisdictions. Tax regulations within each jurisdiction are subject to the interpretation of the related tax laws and regulations and require significant judgment to apply. In accordance with authoritative guidance on accounting for uncertainty in income taxes issued by the Financial Accounting Standards Board (the FASB), the Organization recognizes tax liabilities for uncertain tax positions when it is more likely than not that a tax position will not be sustained upon examination and settlement with various taxing authorities. Liabilities for uncertain tax positions are measured based upon the largest amount of benefit that is greater than 50% likely of being realized upon settlement. The guidance on accounting for uncertainty in income taxes also addresses de-recognition, classification, interest and penalties on income taxes, and accounting in interim periods. Management has evaluated the Organization's tax positions and has concluded that the Organization has no uncertain tax positions that require adjustment to the financial statements to comply with the provisions of this guidance. Income taxes are accounted for under the asset and liability method. Management believes it is no longer subject to income tax examinations for years prior to June 30, 2012.

NOTE 6 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 7 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council on Library and Information Resources defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council on Library and Information Resources contributions. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributions were \$159,078 in 2015.

NOTE 8 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council on Library and Information Resources to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. Bank deposit accounts are insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation ("FDIC") up to a limit of \$250,000. At times during the year, the Organization maintains cash balances in excess of the FDIC insurance limits. Management believes the risk in these situations to be minimal.

The Council on Library and Information Resources received \$6,873,431 from one organization which represents 73 %, of total revenue.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2015

(Continued)

NOTE 9 – Accounts Receivable	June 30, <u>2015</u>
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 786,575
30 – 60 days	3,795
60 – 90 days	27,919
Over 90 days	3,500
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u> -</u>
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>\$ 821,789</u>

NOTE 10 - Commitments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into two noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August, 2018 and April, 2019. The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into a sublease with another organization that it collects rent from which expires August, 2018. Rental expense, for the year ending June 30, 2015 was \$153,095. The Council on Library and Information Resources is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in March 2019.

Future minimum lease payments under all leases net of amounts collected from subtenant with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending <u>June 30,</u>	<u>Capital Lease</u>	<u>Operating Leases</u>	<u>Subtenant Lease</u>	<u>Net Operating Leases</u>
2016	4,260	418,944	(261,582)	157,362
2017	4,260	432,489,	(270,738)	161,751
2018	4,260	446,479	(280,214)	166,265
2019	3,195	155,780	(48,057)	107,723
2020 and beyond	-	-	(-)	-
Total minimum lease payments	<u>\$ 15,975</u>	<u>\$1,453,692</u>	<u>\$ (860,591)</u>	<u>\$ 593,101</u>
Less: Amount representing interest.	<u>(2,101)</u>			
Present value of net minimum lease payments	<u>\$ 13,874</u>			

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2015
(Concluded)

NOTE 11 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments

The carrying amounts reflected in the balance sheets for cash, cash equivalents, loans and notes payable approximate the respective fair values due to the short maturities of those instruments. SFAS 157 requires a fair value hierarchy to be used to prioritize valuation inputs into three levels:

Level 1 – Quoted prices (unadjusted) in active markets for identical assets or liabilities.

Level 2 – Observable inputs other than the quoted prices included in Level 1.

Level 3 – Unobservable inputs.

Fair values of assets and liabilities measured on a nonrecurring basis at June 30, 2015 are as follows:

	Fair Value	(Level 1)	(Level 2)	(Level 3)	(Losses)
Description					
Long-lived assets held for sale	\$ 2,024,313	—	\$ 2,024,313	\$ -	-

Long-lived assets have been valued using a market approach. The values were determined using market prices of similar long-lived assets.

NOTE 12 – Other Income

Other income consists of the following:

Webinar and other fees	<u>\$ 14,163</u>
Total Other Income	<u>\$ 14,163</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
 SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
 For The Year Ended June 30, 2015

	Digital Infrastructure	Outreach and Collaboration	Leadership, Education, and Cultivation	Preservation and Access	Other Strategic Initiatives	Scholarship and Research	Development	Communications and Publications	Total Program	Administration	Total
Employee costs	\$ 328,371	\$ 128,243	\$ 34,520	\$ 315,032	\$ 74,683	\$ 231,145	\$ 24,954	\$ 189,433	\$ 1,326,381	\$ 170,393	\$ 1,496,774
Professional Services and contracts	46,883	-	24,000	93,356	-	99,913	6,250	53,080	323,482	34,665	358,147
Fellowships, scholarships and interns	23,446	434	3,566	6,000	-	1,432,905	-	-	1,466,351	550	1,466,901
Grants Awarded	-	-	-	3,985,391	-	20,000	-	-	4,005,391	-	4,005,391
Communications	11,230	10,035	4,584	1,723	89	2,163	444	14,617	44,885	40,407	85,292
Travel and meetings	428,621	128,029	144,408	117,299	2,422	226,861	-	-	1,047,640	85,925	1,133,565
Publications	-	-	-	17,178	-	1,000	-	14,097	32,275	-	32,275
Registration management fees	14,394	-	-	806	-	-	-	-	15,200	-	15,200
Office operations	20,667	-	2,748	7,504	-	14,418	4,390	1,694	51,421	271,852	323,273
Indirect	15,161	3,027	-	18,831	-	33,620	-	-	70,639	(70,639)	-
Total	\$ 888,773	\$ 269,768	\$ 213,826	\$ 4,563,120	\$ 77,194	\$ 2,062,025	\$ 36,038	\$ 274,921	\$ 8,883,665	\$ 533,153	\$ 8,916,818

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.